

IMPROVING THE ABILITY OF YOUNG PEOPLE TO USE THE INTERNET CORRECTLY

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Abstract: This article talks about the urgent importance of improving the ability to use the Internet correctly, strengthening immunity against foreign ideas entering through the international network.

Key word: Internet, information attack, global network, platform.

Today, the Internet has become an integral part of the life of people of all ages. It is the Internet that gives them the opportunity to communicate with relatives and friends who are in another city or even in the same country. Here you can find almost all the information you are interested in.

It is becoming more and more important to improve the ability of young people to use the Internet correctly, to strengthen their immunity against foreign ideas entering through the international network. At the moment, the information attack is intensifying around the world. We need to be aware of the actions that are being taken to poison the minds of our children through such information attacks, thereby damaging our national values, and protect our youth from them. cause. Children should learn about the correct use of the global network and how to spend time on the Internet profitably.

It is known that the use of the Internet tool is not obligatory for anyone, and it should be based on the law and the rules of the person's own thinking, as well as the standard requirements, that is, the correct selection of information from the Internet network. is appropriate. It can be seen that the scale of information contained in this network tool is so wide and numerous that it sometimes makes it difficult for us to extract the information we need. Today, most financial transactions are carried out over the Internet, online offices are convenient, but on the Internet, security measures should also be taken into account: never share card information; if employers commit fraud, create a second card for payments, then losses will be minimal.

The Internet has become an integral part of the lives of people of all ages today. It can serve for good. With the help of the Internet, people can communicate, have fun, search for necessary information and even earn money. However, the Internet is known for its many negative aspects. They apply to both children and adults. There are certain dangers on the Internet. The Internet can be good or bad. Therefore, it is important to properly use the opportunities provided by the network. According to statistics, about 10 million children under the age of 14 use the Internet in our country. Representatives of the older generation also actively use the possibilities of the World Wide Web. What is interesting on the Internet? It is a world full of information, entertainment and communication. Many people lack this in life. Children start using the Internet at the age of 4 (on average). About 85% of the young generation under the age of 12 actively use the World Wide Web for communication and

entertainment. According to the same statistics, about 52% of children under the age of 14 visit sites that are prohibited for viewing at this age. This can have a significant impact on the baby's psyche, personality formation and later life. However, even without accessing such sites, children may be exposed to other risks. Doctors of the country noticed that the young generation is becoming weaker and less physically developed. Because of this, various diseases appear. Children's immunity stops fighting even simple diseases by itself. The harm of the Internet is different. They do not exclude adults either. No one is free from such negative effects. Different dangers on the Internet are important for both children and adults. If basic safety standards are not followed, the risk of the Internet to people can be great. The Internet is the founder of "mass culture" that is entering the lives of young people today. All kinds of bad, harmful information coming from the Internet is corrupting the minds of our youth and making them become apathetic and lazy. In addition, some inconvenient factors in working with the Network may appear regardless of age. Both adults and the younger generation can become addicted to virtual reality. Today, there are many games, platforms for communication, etc., which can seem more interesting, brighter than ordinary life. Therefore, adults and children can sit for hours on a computer monitor or laptop. In our country, wide opportunities have been created for the use of the Internet. However, some young people do not have the skills to use Internet information correctly and appropriately. Taking this into account, we understand the need to improve the efficiency of work on the formation of a safe Internet environment, strengthening the skills of information acquisition and analysis among young people.

References:

Sattorov A. Informatics and information technologies. Textbook for academic listey and vocational colleges. - T.: "Teacher", 2002.

O.O. Hoshimov, M.M. Tulyaganov. Computer and digital technologies (Textbook for students). -Tashkent, 2009.

<https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet>

<https://library.ziyonet.uz/ru/book/67939>

